

Numerical Study of Viscous Flow Behavior during Cylindrical Particle Rotation

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Received: Oct 01, 2025

Accepted: Nov 04, 2025

Published: Nov 07, 2025

Abstract-- Particle rotation in a viscous fluid flow significantly affects the hydrodynamic structure of the flow, causing the so-called Magnus force. This paper examines the rotation of a circular cylinder in a viscous fluid flow. The effect of the inlet flow on the flow structure in a flat pipe is investigated as the cylinder rotates perpendicular to the flow direction. The drag and lift forces acting on the cylinder are analyzed. Flow calculations were performed using the SIMPLE algorithm.

Keywords: rotating cylinder, Magnus force, viscous fluid, cylinder resistance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Magnus effect is widely used in various technological processes [1, 2]. When a non-uniform flow passes across a cylinder, not only drag forces but also lift forces arise. If the flow is uniform, there is no lift force. However, when the cylinder rotates, a lift force appears, directed perpendicular to the flow. In [3], infinite viscous flow past a rotating cylinder was studied using the Navier-Stokes equations in the streamfunction and vorticity variables. Work [4] is devoted to the Magnus effect for a rotating cylinder in a linear infinite flow based on unsteady equations of a viscous fluid in the streamfunction and vorticity variables. In [5], the effect of rotational speed on laminar flow around a circular cylinder was numerically studied. It was found that increasing rotational speed suppresses vortex separation, leads to unsteady periodic motion at medium-high speeds, and ultimately stabilizes the flow in a steady state. The work [6] examines the effect of cylinder rotation on a viscous fluid in terms of the streamfunction and vorticity variables. Using the equations of a viscous fluid in natural variables, the rotation of a cylinder in a uniform flow was studied in [7]. The effect of cylinder rotation on Poiseuille flow is addressed in [8], where the drag and lift characteristics of a stationary cylinder are analyzed. The Magnus effect in Couette flow is considered in [9].

When modeling flow with particles (both moving [10, 11] and stationary [12–15]), difficulties arise in determining the interaction coefficients. To calculate them, a single-particle cellular model is used, which serves to close the differential equations.

The objective of this work is to determine the hydrodynamic characteristics of flow past a rotating circular cylinder by numerically modeling two-dimensional laminar flow at the inlet section, based on stationary equations of an incompressible fluid in natural variables.

II. MATHEMATICAL AND NUMERICAL MODEL

A. Problem Statement

We consider the flow of a viscous fluid in a flat pipe. A uniform flow is introduced through the pipe inlet. The x-axis is directed along the bottom wall of the pipe, and the y-axis is perpendicular

to it. The pipe height is denoted as H . The point $(x, H/2)$ is the center of a cylinder of radius R which can rotate around its axis. By changing the x -coordinate, the cylinder's position can be varied.

B. Mathematical Model and Boundary Conditions

A uniform flow is specified at the inlet of a flat pipe. Depending on the position and rotation of the cylinder, the lift force varies across the cross-section. The flow is assumed to be incompressible, so the two-dimensional dimensionless Navier-Stokes equations are used [16].

The Navier-Stokes equations in dimensionless form are:

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \Delta u, \quad u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\text{Re}} \Delta v, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0. \quad (2)$$

Calculations are performed in the region excluding the cylinder, for various values of the Reynolds number Re and rotation rate $\alpha (\text{Re} = UH/\nu)$, where U is the average velocity, H is the channel width, ν is the kinematic viscosity coefficient; $\alpha = \omega H/U$, where ω is the angular velocity of the cylinder. The particle center is located at points $(x, 1/2)$, where x varies.

Boundary Conditions:

- A uniform flow is specified at the inlet of the pipe:

$$u = 1, \quad v = 0, \quad p = p_0.$$

- No-slip conditions are applied on the pipe walls:

$$u = 0, \quad v = 0.$$

- Conditions are used at the output:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0.$$

C. Numerical Model

The SIMPLE algorithm described in [17, 18] is used to numerically solve the Navier-Stokes equations (1)–(2) with given boundary conditions. A staggered nonuniform grid is used. The main grid, where the pressure is determined, is constructed so that its nodes are located on the cylinder surface (a consistent grid [19]). Since the flow is strongly deformed near the cylinder, a nonuniform grid of size 50×40 is used. When the cylinder's position changes, the grid is rebuilt. The cylinder surface is divided into 10 nodes (20 nodes are selected on the surface). After discretization, the resulting equations are solved using the relaxation method.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Flow Structure near a Rotating Cylinder

To analyze the effect of cylinder rotation on the flow structure (at various positions in the inlet section), calculations were performed using flow parameters and a dimensionless cylinder radius. Figure 1 shows the longitudinal velocity profiles at different angular velocity values for a cylinder centered at (0.2,0.5).

Fig. 1. Longitudinal Velocity Profiles near a Cylinder

The velocity profiles in Figure 1 reflect changes in the longitudinal velocity in three cross-sections: in front of the cylinder ($x=0.1$), at the center ($x=0.2$), and behind the cylinder ($x=0.3136$). The symmetrical velocity profile observed for a stationary cylinder (Fig. 1(a)) changes significantly with increasing rotation intensity, breaking the symmetry (Figs. 1(b) and 1(c)).

A more detailed representation of the directions of the velocity field near a stationary cylinder at $Re = 200$ is shown in Fig. 2 for the center at point (0.2, 0.5) and in Fig. 3 for (1.0, 0.5).

Fig. 2. Velocity direction field (cylinder center at point (0.2, 0.5)).

Fig. 3. Velocity direction field (cylinder center at point (1.0, 0.5)).

Comparison of Figs. 2 and 3 shows similarity in the direction of the velocity field (circulation motion), but the resistance strongly depends on the inlet flow. Cylinder rotation leads to the disappearance of the circulation motion behind the cylinder, observed when the cylinder is stationary (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Velocity direction field (cylinder center at point (0.2, 0.5)), $Re=100$, $\alpha=10$.

Fig. 5. Velocity direction field (cylinder center at point (1.0, 0.5)), Re=100, $\alpha=10$.

In Fig. 5, the velocity field demonstrates that the two circulation flows behind the cylinder, characteristic of the stationary case, disappear when a uniform flow passes around the rotating cylinder. As the cylinder moves away from the inlet section, the upper circulation zone deforms, and the lower one disappears. Further increase in rotation intensity leads to the complete disappearance of reverse flows.

B. Calculating Forces for a Rotating Cylinder

The dimensionless drag force per unit cylinder length is calculated using the formula:

$$D = \int_0^{2\pi} \left[-p \cos \theta + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \sin \theta + 2 \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \cos \theta \right] r d\theta = D_p + D_\tau$$

where D_p is the contribution of pressure forces, and D_τ is the contribution of viscous forces.

TABLE I
DRAG FORCE

		Re=100			Re=200		
		(0.2;0.5)	(0.5;0.5)	(1;0.5)	(0.2;0.5)	(0.5;0.5)	(1;0.5)
$\alpha=0$	D	50.71	37.78	39.28	78.36	55.71	56.70
	D_p	37.68	27.51	28.14	64.03	49.56	45.42
	D_τ	13.03	10.27	10.64	14.33	11.15	11.28
$\alpha=10$	D	51.13	36.86	38.51	79.11	53.68	54.83
	D_p	38.47	27.00	28.35	65.18	43.39	44.47
	D_τ	12.66	9.86	10.16	13.93	10.27	10.36
$\alpha=20$	D	52.58	33.48	35.44	82.53	46.73	47.94
	D_p	40.88	24.63	26.46	70.79	38.41	39.71
	D_τ	11.70	8.85	8.98	11.72	8.32	8.23

Dimensionless lift force per unit cylinder length:

$$L = \int_0^{2\pi} \left[-p \sin \theta + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \cos \theta + 2 \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \sin \theta \right] r d\theta = L_p + L_\tau$$

where L_p is the contribution of pressure forces, and L_τ is the contribution of viscous forces.

Table I shows the values of the dimensionless drag force depending on the cylinder position, Reynolds number, and rotation rate. Trends similar to [14, 15] are observed: the contribution of pressure forces predominates over friction forces. The drag force depends strongly on the cylinder position in the inlet section: it is maximum at the inlet, then decreases, with a slight increase at the point (1, 0.5). This is true for all values of α . Close to the inlet, the drag increases with α , and further away, it decreases, regardless of Re. An increase in Re increases the drag for all α .

TABLE II
LIFT DRAG FORCE

		Re=100			Re=200		
		(0.2;0.5)	(0.5;0.5)	(1;0.5)	(0.2;0.5)	(0.5;0.5)	(1;0.5)
$\alpha=10$	L	-30.48	-28.33	-28.87	-51.42	-46.37	-46.67
	L_p	--29.65	-26.86	-27.55	-51.40	-45.21	-45.64
	L_τ	-0.83	-1.47	-1.32	-0.02	-1.16	-1.03
$\alpha=20$	L	-62.20	-57.48	-58.22	-111.23	-98.19	-98.39
	L_p	-60.41	-54.64	-55.62	-109.48	-95.38	-95.74
	L_τ	-1.79	-2.84	-2.60	-1.75	-2.81	-2.65

Table II displays the lift results, demonstrating the significant influence of rotation on lift generation. In the absence of rotation, there is no lift due to the symmetry of the flow. The main contribution comes from pressure forces. Rotation has a slight effect on drag (less than 12%), but a significant effect on lift, which can exceed drag. Doubling the angular velocity almost doubles the lift. The influence of the Reynolds number is also noticeable.

IV. CONCLUSION

When a uniform flow is introduced into a flat pipe, no-slip conditions create an initial region at the inlet where the flow transitions from uniform to Poiseuille. Placing a rotating cylinder at different points in this region allowed us to study the effect of rotation on the hydrodynamic characteristics. It was found that near the inlet, drag and lift reach a maximum and then decrease. An increase in the Reynolds number increases both drag and lift due to rotation.

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